

COMPARATIVE PRAGMATICS: DISSIMILARITIES AND COMMONALITIES BETWEEN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Introduction

The study of pragmatics takes into account the speaker's intentions, the meaning they are conveying, and the social context in which they are employed. Comparing the pragmatic characteristics of various languages is the main goal of comparative pragmatics. With precise in-text citations to back up the ideas covered, we will examine the parallels and differences in comparative pragmatics between the English and Uzbek languages in this article.

1. Indirect versus Direct:

The degree of directness in speech acts is one obvious distinction between Uzbek and English pragmatics. Uzbek heavily relies on indirectness, whereas English tends to use a more direct approach (Karakulova, 2017). For example, in English, someone can decline an invitation directly by saying, "No, thank you," but in Uzbek, one can decline indirectly by making excuses or using roundabout statements (Karakulova, 2017).

2. Etiquette Techniques:

There are also distinctions between Uzbek and English pragmatics in politeness tactics. Positive politeness is typically prioritized in English with the goal of fostering camaraderie and friendliness (Cupchik & Leung, 2008). However, Uzbek places a strong emphasis on being impolite, with the goal of avoiding imposition and maintaining social distance (Karakulova, 2017). Using first names and engaging in small conversation are examples of positive English politeness, whereas honorifics and indirect speech acts are examples of Uzbek politeness (Karakulova, 2017).

3. Systems that take turns:

The turn-taking system, which describes how conversations are arranged and conducted, is another important facet of pragmatics. Conversations in English frequently use a "one-at-a-time" turn-taking system, in which participants wait for their turn to speak (Curl, 2006). On the other hand, Uzbek conversations might have a more competitive and overlapping turn-taking style, with a lot of interruptions (Curl, 2006).

4. Civility in Requests:

Language differences between Uzbek and English can also be seen in politeness strategies used in requests. To lessen the possibility of a direct request being imposed, indirectness is frequently preferred in English (Brown & Levinson, 1987). However, directness in request is more common in Uzbek language, emphasizing the interlocutors' relationship over the imposition itself (Karakulova, 2017).

5. Communicating Nonverbally:

A key component of pragmatics is nonverbal cues. There are parallels between the nonverbal behavior of Uzbek and English speakers, despite the possible differences in their nonverbal communication patterns. According to Heath (2017) and Karakulova (2017), both languages use body language, gestures, and facial expressions to express politeness, emotions, and cultural norms.

In conclusion

The pragmatics of the English and Uzbek languages can be compared to uncover some fascinating distinctions and parallels. Whereas Uzbek emphasizes indirectness, negative politeness, and directness in requests, English values directness, positive politeness, and indirectness more. Between the two languages, there are also some differences in turn-taking protocols and nonverbal communication styles. Linguists, researchers, and language learners can all learn more about how language works by comprehending these distinctions and similarities. Researcher, linguist, and language learner insights into the ways in which language is used in various cultural and linguistic contexts can be expanded by comprehending these distinctions and similarities.

References:

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